

Mapping Research Topics on Price to Book Value (PBV) Ratio in Islamic and Conventional Banking: VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Literature Review

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Abstract

This study aims to determine the research mapping regarding the Price to Book Value (PBV) ratio in Islamic and Conventional Banking using a mix-method approach, namely the VOSviewer bibliometric study and literature review. Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping the distribution of journal publications around the PBV ratio; (2) mapping the results of the VOSviewer bibliometric visualization around the PBV ratio based on the number of clusters and their items; and (3) mapping research topics around the PBV ratio using a literature review study. The results showed that: (1) based on the distribution of journal publications, there were 385 journal publications regarding the PBV ratio; (2) based on the mapping of the VOSviewer bibliometric study, the network visualization results around the PBV ratio are divided into 4 clusters and 113 topic items; (3) based on the mapping of literature review studies, there are 27 topics around the influence of the PBV ratio and 61 topics about the determinants of the PBV ratio. The implications and contributions of this research are to map research topics around PBV ratios in Islamic and Conventional Banking which are often or rarely researched by researchers so that they can be a reference for subsequent researchers.

Keywords: Price to Book Value (PBV), Bibliometrics, VOSviewer, Literature Review, Islamic and Conventional Banking

Introduction

In the banking industry, Price to Book Value (PBV) is an important financial ratio because it can provide important information for investors and analysts in assessing bank valuation, bank performance and investment risk in banks. For example, PBV can be used to compare the valuation of one bank with another. This can help investors and analysts assess whether a bank is valued too high or too low compared to its competitors. Apart from that, PBV can also be used to assess banking performance. The higher the PBV of a bank, the better its performance in generating profits for its shareholders. PBV can also be used in fundamental analysis to assess the feasibility of investing in a bank. In this case, PBV is used to compare the valuation of bank shares with their book value.

PBV can also be a tool for measuring investment risk in a bank. The higher the PBV of a bank, the higher the investment risk in that bank. A low PBV at a certain time can be an indication that the bank's shares are priced cheaply, while a high PBV can be an indication that the bank's shares are priced expensively. Changes in PBV may occur over time. This can be caused by changes in market valuation or changes in the bank's book value. A low PBV at a certain time can be an indication that the bank's shares are priced cheaply, while a high PBV can be an indication that the bank's shares are priced expensively. Overall, PBV remains relevant today and can provide important information for investors and analysts in assessing banking valuation, banking

performance, investment risk, as well as changes in market valuation and bank book value over time. PBV can be a very useful tool in helping investors and analysts make the right investment decisions in the banking industry.

Research on the PBV ratio in banking continues to develop along with developments in the banking industry and financial markets in general. Several important developments in research on PBV in banking include: first, research that develops a better PBV model in assessing banking valuation. For example, PBV models that consider factors such as profits, bank size, risk, and asset quality have been developed and tested. Models like this can provide more accurate information regarding banking valuations and enable investors and analysts to make better investment decisions. Second, research that compares the use of PBV between Islamic banks and conventional banks. The study results show that Islamic banks have a higher PBV compared to conventional banks, even though the investment risk in Islamic banks tends to be higher. Studies like this provide important information for investors and analysts in comparing valuations between Islamic banks and conventional banks. Third, research shows that PBV can be a strong indicator for predicting bank financial performance in the future. This kind of study can help investors and analysts in choosing bank shares that will have good financial performance in the future. Fourth, research is used in portfolio analysis to select the most attractive bank shares in terms of valuation. Recent studies show that PBV can be used as a factor in selecting the most attractive bank shares in an investment portfolio. Fifth, PBV is not only used in the banking industry in Indonesia, but is also used in global financial markets. Recent studies have shown that PBV can be an important indicator in selecting bank shares in global financial markets. Overall, research on PBV in banking continues to develop and provides important information for investors and analysts in assessing banking valuation, bank performance, investment risk and portfolio development. Recent studies and the development of better PBV models can help investors and analysts make more informed investment decisions based on more accurate information.

The aim of this research is to map research topics around PBV in Sharia and Conventional Banking by using: (1) VOSviewer bibliometric studies to analyze and study maps of literature developments in publications in a scientific field by creating metadata network maps; and (2) literature study review to analyze, identify and review articles from the accredited national journal Sinta. The difference between this research and previous research is that this research explains all research topics surrounding PBV. This can be a reference for other researchers who wish to research PBV. The implication and contribution of this research is to map research topics regarding the PBV ratio in Sharia and Conventional Banking which are often or rarely researched by researchers, so that they can become a reference for subsequent researchers.

Literature Review

Price to Book Value (PBV) is a financial ratio that measures the comparison between the market price of a company's shares and its book value. PBV is often used in the banking industry to assess the market value of a bank compared to its book value. In a banking context, book value consists of total equity minus the value of preferred shares and other liabilities. PBV is the comparison between the market price of a company's shares and its book value per share. If PBV is more than 1, it means the market values the company at more than its book value, and if PBV is less than 1, then the market values the

company at less than its book value. PBV can be used as an indicator of whether a bank is trading at an overvalued (expensive) or undervalued (cheap) price. However, PBV only provides a limited picture and should be used in conjunction with other financial ratios to get a more complete picture of a company's health and value.

Bibliometric studies are a quantitative analysis method used to study the characteristics and trends of scientific publications using bibliographic data, such as journal articles, books, or conference proceedings. These studies can help to identify patterns and trends in scholarly production, publications, and citations, as well as understand the role and impact of research in a field. Bibliometric studies usually include measurements of the number of publications, number of citations, and qualitative analysis of the documents. Some indicators that are often used in bibliometric studies include: number of publications, number of citations, journal impact factor, Hirsch index, and measurement of collaboration between researchers. Bibliometric studies can be carried out in various fields of science, including social sciences, natural sciences, medicine, and information technology. This study can help to understand trends in the development of science and technology, as well as provide important information for decision making in planning research and development activities.

VOSviewer is one of the software used for bibliometric analysis and network visualization. This software was developed by Nees Jan van Eck and Ludo Waltman from the Center for Science and Technology Studies (CWTS) at Leiden University, the Netherlands. VOSviewer can be used to analyze bibliographic data, such as journal articles, books, or conference proceedings. With VOSviewer, users can carry out network analysis, clustering analysis, co-citation analysis, co-occurrence analysis, and create visualizations of the results of the analysis. VOSviewer can help to identify relationships between topics and authors in a research field. This software can be used in various fields of science, including social sciences, natural sciences, medicine, and information technology. VOSviewer can also help researchers understand trends in the development of science and technology, as well as provide important information for decision making in planning research and development activities. VOSviewer is free to use and is available for download from the official website of the Center for Science and Technology Studies (CWTS) at Leiden University, the Netherlands.

Studies literature review is a type of study that collects and analyzes data from scientific publications and literature relevant to a particular topic or research problem. This study was conducted to identify, evaluate, and summarize existing research findings, as well as to identify gaps in research that could become topics for further research. Literature review studies are usually carried out by searching for and reviewing scientific publications, such as journals, books and theses, which are related to the research topic you want to research. Then, data from these publications is analyzed using qualitative or quantitative methods to identify important findings and describe research trends. Literature review studies are often carried out as an initial stage in research, so they can help identify research problems that need to be resolved, evaluate weaknesses in previous research, and identify areas of research that are still less studied. Literature study reviews can also be conducted as independent studies aimed at providing a comprehensive understanding of a particular topic. The results of a literature review study are usually represented in the form of a summary or report that describes the key findings and synthesis

of the literature reviewed. Literature review studies can be carried out in various fields of science, including social sciences, natural sciences, and engineering.

Methodology

This research uses research methods with a mix-method approach, namely quantitative methods in bibliometric studies and qualitative methods in literature review studies. The research object is Price to Book Value (PBV). The type of data used is secondary data. The scope of the data used is research journal articles on PBV in Sharia and Conventional Banking.

The source of data collection comes from search for accredited national journals, Sinta via the Garuda website (Digital Reference Garba) and Perish/Harzing software. Data analysis tools use Microsoft Excel software, Mendeley Desktop, and VOSviewer. Data collection techniques include: (1) opening Perish/Harzing software, then search for journals based on the title words category with the keywords " Price to Book Value " and " PBV " throughout the year; (2) collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles; (3) download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) formats from all journals for which data has been collected; and (4) inserting the RIS data file into Mendeley Desktop software.

Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping the distribution of journal publications regarding PBV using Microsoft Excel and Mendeley Desktop based on publication year; (2) mapping bibliometric network visualization results and journal publication trends around PBV using the VOSviewer (Visualization of Similarities) algorithm software based on the number of clusters and items; and (3) mapping research topics around PBV using a literature review study.

Results and Discussion

Mapping the Distribution of Scientific Publications around Price to Book Value (PBV) in Sharia and Conventional Banking

There are 385 national journals accredited by Sinta based on the results of data collection using Microsoft Excel and Mendeley Desktop originating from the Garuda website (Digital Reference Garba) and Perish/Harzing software during the period 2003 to 2023. The results are as follows:

Table 1. Journal publication data regarding PBV by year

Year	Number of Publications	Year	Number of Publications
2003	1	2015	25
2004	1	2016	31
2005	1	2017	32
2009	1	2018	20
2010	2	2019	37
2011	2	2020	42
2012	11	2021	61
2013	11	2022	72
2014	27	2023	8

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2016.

VOSviewer Bibliometric Study Mapping Regarding Price to Book Value (PBV) in Sharia and Conventional Banking

liquidity, path analysis, profitability, relationship, research method, role, significance level, significant impact, t test, total asset turnover.

- Cluster 4 consists of 2 topic items, namely: assets, roa.

Mapping Literature Review Studies around the Influence of Price to Book Value (PBV) in Sharia and Conventional Banking

Literature review study in previous research journals, researchers found 27 influences of PBV on Sharia and Conventional Banking, namely:

(1) Stock beta. A stock's beta is a measure of the systematic risk associated with overall market price fluctuations. PBV in banking does not have a direct influence on stock beta. However, a high PBV can indicate that the company has a low book value compared to its share price, which can influence investors to increase demand for shares, thereby reducing the systematic risk or stock beta.

(2) Beneish M-Score. Beneish M-Score is a method for detecting potential manipulation of a company's financial statements. PBV in banking does not have a direct influence on the Beneish M-Score. However, a low PBV can indicate that the company has a high book value compared to its share price, which can indicate that the company has no potential for manipulation of its financial statements.

(3) Debt to Total Asset Ratio. DTA is a ratio that measures the level of debt use by a company to finance its assets. PBV in banking has a different influence on DTA. A low PBV can indicate that the company has a high book value compared to its share price, which can indicate that the company has a good ability to manage its debt so that it can reduce DTA.

(4) Debt to Equity Ratio/DER. DER is a ratio that measures the level of use of debt and equity by a company to finance its operations. PBV in banking has a different influence on DER. A low PBV can indicate that the company has a high book value compared to its share price, which can indicate that the company has a good ability to manage its debt so that it can reduce the DER. However, a high PBV can indicate that the company is carrying out aggressive expansion using debt so that it can increase DER.

(5) Dividend Payout Ratio/DPR. DPR measures the percentage of a company's net profit that is paid as dividends to shareholders. PBV in banking has a different influence on DPR. A high PBV can indicate that the company is experiencing a significant increase in market value, so the company may consider retaining some of its profits as investment, which can reduce the DPR.

(6) Earnings Response Coefficient/ERC. ERC measures the relationship between company earnings announcements and changes in stock prices. PBV in banking does not have a direct influence on ERC. However, a low PBV can indicate that the company has a high book value compared to its share price, which can influence investors to increase demand for shares, thereby increasing ERC.

(7) Earnings Per Share/EPS. EPS measures the company's profit generated per share. PBV in banking does not have a direct influence on EPS. However, a high PBV can indicate that the company is experiencing a significant increase in market value, so the company may consider retaining some of its profits as an investment, which can affect EPS.

(8) Earnings Management. Earning Management is a company's practice of managing its financial reports to achieve certain goals. PBV in banking has a different influence on Earning Management. A low PBV can indicate that the

company has a high book value compared to its share price, which can minimize earnings practices Management. However, a high PBV can trigger Earnings Management practices because the company wants to maintain its financial performance to support the increase in its share market value.

(9) Share price. PBV can influence share prices in the market. A low PBV can indicate that shares are undervalued and can be a signal for investors to buy these shares, thereby increasing demand for shares and share prices. A high PBV can indicate that the stock is overvalued and can be a signal for investors to sell the stock, thereby reducing the stock price.

(10) Dividend policy. PBV in banking can influence the dividend policy adopted by the company. A low PBV may indicate that the company does not have a high market value, so the company may choose to pay higher dividends to shareholders as a return on their investment. A high PBV can indicate that the company has a high market value, so the company may choose to retain some of its profits as investment, which can reduce its dividend policy.

(11) Investment decisions. PBV in banking can influence company investment decisions. A low PBV can be a signal for a company to invest in a business that has the potential to generate higher profits, because the company's book value is lower compared to the market price of its shares. A high PBV can be a signal for a company to hold investment, because the company's book value is higher than the market price of its shares.

(12) Stock split decision. PBV in banking can influence stock split decisions taken by companies. Stock split is a decision to divide existing shares into more shares at a lower price. A low PBV can be a signal for a company to carry out a stock split, because low share prices can increase investors' purchasing power and increase demand for shares. A high PBV can make a company reluctant to carry out a stock split, because the company may believe that a high share price reflects high company value.

(13) Market performance. PBV can influence the market performance of a company on the stock exchange. A low PBV can indicate that the stock is undervalued, so it can attract investors to buy the stock and increase demand for the stock. A high PBV can indicate that shares are overvalued, which can reduce investors' interest in buying these shares and reduce demand for shares.

(14) Company value. PBV can be used to measure company value. A low PBV can indicate that the company is valued at a low value compared to the assets owned by the company, so it can be a signal to buy shares and can increase the value of the company. A high PBV can indicate that the company is valued at a high value compared to the assets owned by the company, so it can be a signal to sell shares and can reduce the value of the company.

(15) Distribution of dividends. PBV in banking can influence the company's dividend distribution policy. A low PBV can indicate that the company is valued at a low value compared to the assets it owns, so the company may choose to pay higher dividends as a return on shareholder investment.

(16) Stock valuation. PBV can be used to assess whether a share is priced fairly or not. A low PBV can indicate that the stock is undervalued and may be a signal for investors to buy the stock. A high PBV can indicate that the stock is overvalued and may be a signal for investors to sell the stock. Accurate stock valuation can help investors make the right investment decisions.

(17) Valuation of company equity. PBV can be used as a method of assessing company equity. A low PBV can indicate that shares are being valued at a low value compared to the assets owned by the company, so it can be a

signal to buy shares. A high PBV can indicate that shares are being valued at a high value compared to the assets owned by the company, so it can be a signal to sell shares.

(18) Voluntary disclosure of intangible assets. PBV can influence the voluntary disclosure of intangible assets by companies. Intangible assets such as goodwill, trademarks, or patents can increase a company's book value, thereby increasing PBV. A company may choose to disclose more information about intangible assets if the company's PBV is relatively low.

(19) Price Earning Ratio/PER. PBV can affect the company's PER. PER is a financial ratio used to measure a company's market value against net income per share. A low PBV can indicate that shares are being priced at a low value compared to their book value, which can increase PER. A high PBV can indicate that shares are being valued at a high value compared to their book value, which can reduce PER.

(20) Stock portfolio return. PBV can influence stock portfolio returns. A stock portfolio containing shares with low PBV can provide the potential for higher returns because these shares may be priced at a low value compared to the assets they own. On the other hand, a stock portfolio containing shares with a high PBV can provide a lower potential return because these shares may be valued at a high value compared to the assets they own.

(21) Return of Share/ROS. PBV can affect ROS or stock returns. ROS measures the profit or loss that investors obtain from investing in shares in a company. A low PBV can indicate that shares are being valued at a low value compared to their book value, which can increase ROS. Conversely, a high PBV can indicate that shares are being valued at a high value compared to their book value, which can reduce ROS.

(22) Return On Assets/ROA. PBV can affect ROA or rate of return on assets. ROA measures a company's ability to generate profits from the assets it owns. A low PBV can indicate that the company is being valued at a low value compared to the value of its assets, which can increase ROA. Conversely, a high PBV can indicate that the company is being valued at a high value compared to the value of its assets, which can reduce ROA.

(23) Return On Equity/ROE. PBV can affect ROE or return on equity. ROE measures a company's ability to generate profits from capital invested by shareholders. A low PBV can indicate that the company is being valued at a low value compared to its equity value, which can increase ROE. Conversely, a high PBV can indicate that the company is being valued at a high value compared to its equity value, which can reduce ROE.

(24) Return of sharia stock issuers. PBV can affect the Return of Sharia Stock Issuers. Sharia stock issuers follow sharia principles in their operational activities, so not all types of investments are acceptable. A low PBV in sharia stock issuers can indicate that the shares are being valued at a low value compared to their book value, so that it can increase returns for sharia stock issuers. On the other hand, a high PBV for sharia stock issuers can indicate that the shares are being valued at a high value compared to their book value, which can reduce returns for sharia stock issuers.

(25) Sales Growth. PBV can influence Sales Growth or sales growth. A low PBV can indicate that shares are being priced at a low value compared to their book value, which can increase investors' interest in buying these shares. In the long term, increased investor interest can affect the company's sales growth. On the other hand, a high PBV can indicate that shares are being valued

at a high value compared to their book value, which can reduce investors' interest in buying these shares.

(26) Stock trading volume. PBV can affect stock trading volume or the number of shares traded. A low PBV can indicate that shares are being priced at a low value compared to their book value, which can increase investors' interest in buying and selling these shares. This can increase stock trading volume. On the other hand, a high PBV can indicate that shares are being valued at a high value compared to their book value, which can reduce investors' interest in buying and selling these shares.

(27) Volume Activity. PBV can affect Volume Activity or stock trading activity. A low PBV can indicate that shares are being priced at a low value compared to their book value, which can increase share trading activity. This can create opportunities for investors to buy and sell these shares. Conversely, a high PBV can indicate that shares are being valued at a high value compared to their book value, which can reduce stock trading activity. This can reduce the opportunity for investors to buy and sell these shares.

Mapping the Literature Review Study regarding the Determinant Variable Price to Book Value (PBV) in Sharia and Conventional Banking

Literature review study in previous research journals, researchers found 61 PBV determinant variables in Sharia and Conventional Banking, namely:

(1) Auditor Switching. Auditor Switching or changing auditors can affect PBV in banking. Changing auditors can be considered a sign of investors' lack of confidence in the quality of the company's financial reports. This can affect the company's share price and PBV. If the change of auditor is associated with non-compliance with financial regulations or other serious problems, then this can reduce the company's PBV.

(2) Tax aggressiveness. Tax aggressiveness or the level of aggressiveness in avoiding or minimizing tax payments can influence PBV in banking. If a company uses a tax aggressiveness strategy to increase its net profit, then this can increase the company's PBV because higher net profit can increase the company's market value. However, if tax aggressiveness is considered a detrimental practice for the company, then this can reduce the company's PBV.

(3) Assets Ratio. Assets Ratio or asset ratio can influence PBV in banking. If a company has a high asset ratio, then this can indicate that the company has many assets that can be used to support future growth and minimize financial risk. This can increase the company's PBV because investors are more interested in companies that have good future growth potential. However, if the asset ratio is considered too high, then this can reduce the company's PBV because investors may view the company as inefficient in managing its assets.

(4) Actuarial Profile. Actuarial Profile can influence PBV in banking. An actuarial profile can provide an overview of the financial risks faced by a company, such as credit risk, market risk and operational risk. If the company's actuarial profile is considered good and shows that the company is able to manage risk well, then this can increase the company's PBV. However, if the actuarial profile is considered poor, then this can reduce the company's PBV because investors may view the company as unable to manage financial risks well.

(5) Actuarial Backup. Actuarial Backup or actuarial reserves can affect PBV in banking. Actuarial reserves are a form of fund allowance made by insurance companies or companies that have actuarial obligations to ensure that these obligations can be fulfilled in the future. If the company has large

enough actuarial reserves, this can increase the company's PBV because investors will have more confidence in the company's ability to fulfill its financial obligations. However, if actuarial reserves are deemed insufficient, then this can reduce the company's PBV because investors may doubt the company's ability to meet its financial obligations in the future.

(6) Basic Earning Power/BEP. BEP or basic income capability can influence PBV in banking. Basic income capability measures how efficient a company is in generating operating profits from the assets it owns. If a company has a high basic income capability, then this can increase the company's PBV because investors will be more interested in companies that are efficient in generating operational profits. However, if the basic income capability is considered low, then this can reduce the company's PBV because investors may view the company as inefficient.

(7) Stock beta. Stock Beta or systematic risk measurement can influence PBV in banking. Stock Beta measures how sensitive a company's stock is to market movements. If a company has a high stock beta, this can increase the risk of the company's shares and reduce the company's PBV. Conversely, if the beta of a company's shares is low, then this can increase the company's PBV because the risk of the company's shares is considered lower.

(8) Financial burden. Financial charges or interest costs can affect PBV in banking. If the company's financial burden is too high, then this can indicate that the company has a large debt burden which can affect its net profit. This can reduce the company's PBV because investors may view the company as having high financial risk. However, if the financial burden is considered too low, then this can increase the company's PBV because investors will see the company as an efficient company in managing its debt.

(9) Operational Costs to Operational Expenses/BOPO. The effect of BOPO on PBV in banking can vary depending on the industry and company situation. In general, the higher the BOPO, the lower the PBV. An increase in BOPO can indicate low efficiency in managing operational costs, which can reduce company performance and market value.

(10) Capital Adequacy Ratio/CAR. CAR is a ratio that shows a bank's ability to meet the minimum capital requirements set by the regulator. The higher the CAR, the greater the bank's ability to overcome risks and withstand losses, which can increase investor confidence and increase PBV.

(11) Capital Turnover. Capital Turnover is a ratio that measures the efficiency of using capital in generating income. The higher this ratio, the more efficient the bank is in generating income from its capital, which can increase PBV.

(12) Capital Expenditure. Capital expenditures can affect PBV in two ways. First, high capital expenditure can indicate that the bank is investing to improve performance and growth, which can increase PBV. Second, high capital expenditure can also indicate that the bank is facing higher risks or requires restructuring, which can reduce PBV.

(13) Corporate Social Responsibility/CSR. The greater the company's commitment to CSR, the higher the company's value in the eyes of society and investors. This can influence PBV positively by increasing the reputation and public trust in the company. However, the effect of CSR on PBV can vary depending on the CSR strategy and implementation carried out by the company.

(14) Current Ratio. Current Ratio is a liquidity ratio that measures a company's ability to meet its short-term obligations. The higher the Current

Ratio, the greater the company's ability to fulfill its short-term obligations, which can increase investor confidence and increase PBV.

(15) Deviation of the Actual Growth Rate from the Sustainable Growth Rate. Deviation from Actual Growth The rate of the Sustainable Growth Rate can influence PBV in two ways. First, if the Actual Growth Rate exceeds the Sustainable Growth Rate, this could indicate unsustainable growth and could reduce PBV. Second, if the Actual Growth Rate is lower than the Sustainable Growth Rate, this can indicate that the company is not optimizing existing growth potential and can reduce PBV.

(16) Degree of Fundamental Leverage. Degree of Fundamental Leverage is a ratio that measures the level of leverage used by a company to generate profits. The higher this ratio, the greater the risk of company bankruptcy and the lower the PBV.

(17) Debt to Asset Ratio/DAR. DAR is a ratio that measures the proportion of company assets financed by debt. The higher this ratio, the greater the risk of company bankruptcy and the lower the PBV.

(18) Dividend Payout Ratio/DPR. DPR is a ratio that measures the proportion of profits paid as dividends to shareholders. The higher the DPR, the greater the profits paid out as dividends and the lower the profits retained for investment and growth, which can reduce PBV. However, a moderate DPR can increase investor confidence and increase PBV by demonstrating a balance between dividend payments and investment for future growth.

(19) Debt to Equity Ratio/DER. DER is a ratio that measures the proportion of funds financed by shareholders and debt. The higher this ratio, the greater the risk of company bankruptcy and the lower the PBV.

(20) Earnings Growth Rate. Earnings Growth Rate measures a company's profit growth from year to year. The higher the Earnings Growth Rate, the greater the potential profit that can be generated and increase PBV.

(21) Earnings Per Share/EPS. EPS is a company's profit calculated per share. The higher the EPS, the higher the possibility of investors to invest in company shares and increase PBV.

(22) Earnings Management. Earning Management is an unethical accounting practice for managing financial reports to improve the appearance of company performance. This practice can harm investors and reduce PBV.

(23) Economic Value Added/EVA. EVA is a company performance evaluation method that measures the added value generated after considering the capital costs incurred. The higher the EVA, the greater the added value generated and can increase PBV. However, EVA must be viewed in the context of the same industry to draw accurate conclusions.

(24) Financial Leverage. Financial Leverage measures how much a company uses debt to finance operations and investments. The higher the Financial Leverage, the greater the risk of company bankruptcy and the lower the PBV.

(25) Good Corporate Governance/GCG. GCG is good corporate governance practices, including transparency, accountability and shareholder involvement. The better the company's GCG, the greater investor confidence and the PBV can increase.

(26) Growth. Growth refers to the company's growth from year to year. The higher the growth rate, the higher the potential profits that can be generated and can increase PBV.

(27) Gross Domestic Product/GDP. GDP measures a country's economic output. The higher the GDP, the greater investor confidence in the country's economy and the PBV of companies in that sector can increase.

(28) Inflation. Inflation can affect PBV in banking because it can affect the value of company assets and liabilities. If inflation rises, the value of company assets will also rise and PBV can increase. However, if inflation rises significantly, operational costs will also rise and this can affect profits and PBV.

(29) International Financial Reporting Standards/IFRS. IFRS is an international accounting standard used by companies to prepare financial reports. The use of IFRS can increase company transparency and accountability, and provide confidence to investors. In terms of PBV, the use of IFRS can improve the quality of information available to investors, thereby increasing the company's PBV.

(30) Intellectual Capital. Intellectual Capital is an invisible resource in the form of physical assets, such as expertise, experience and technology. Intellectual Capital Management can improve company performance and make it more competitive. In terms of PBV, if the company is able to manage Intellectual Capital well and utilize it to improve performance and profits, then PBV can increase.

(31) Financial performance. PBV is influenced by the company's financial performance, such as Return on Assets (ROA) and Return on Equity (ROE). Companies that are able to achieve high ROA and ROE tend to have higher PBV because investors believe that these companies can generate greater profits.

(32) Managerial ownership. Managerial ownership also has an influence on PBV. Companies owned by management or insiders tend to have higher PBV because they have greater access to internal company information and tend to have greater motivation to increase company value.

(33) Dividend policy. Dividend policy can influence PBV. Companies that pay stable and consistent dividends tend to have higher PBV because investors consider these dividends to be a stable and attractive source of income. However, companies that do not pay dividends or pay inconsistent dividends may have a lower PBV because investors perceive the company to have a higher level of risk.

(34) Investment decisions. Banking investment decisions can affect a company's financial performance, including Price to Book Value (PBV). If banks make profitable investments and can increase profits, then PBV will likely increase due to increased profits and company value. However, if the investment made is less successful or even detrimental, then PBV can decrease due to a decrease in company value.

(35) Net profit. Net profit or net income is one of the factors that can influence PBV. If net profit increases, the company value increases, so PBV can increase. Conversely, if net profit decreases, PBV may decrease.

(36) Liquidity. Banking liquidity can affect PBV. If banking liquidity is good, PBV can increase because the company can fulfill its obligations and take better investment opportunities. However, if liquidity is poor, then PBV may fall due to greater risk of default and inability to make profitable investments.

(37) Loan to Deposit Ratio/LDR. LDR is the ratio between total credit provided by the bank and total deposits received by the bank. The higher the LDR, the greater the risk of default at the bank because the credit provided is greater than the deposits received. This can reduce investor confidence in banking performance so that PBV can decrease.

(38) Long term Debt to Equity Ratio. This ratio shows how much long-term debt is used compared to equity in financing the company's operational activities. The higher this ratio, the greater the risk of bankruptcy for the company and it can reduce investor confidence in the company's performance so that PBV can decrease.

(39) Net Interest Margin/NIM. NIM is the difference between interest income received by the bank and interest costs incurred by the bank. The higher the NIM, the greater the profits obtained by the bank and improve banking performance. This can increase investor confidence in the company so that PBV can increase.

(40) Net Profit Margin/NPM. NPM is a ratio that measures a bank's effectiveness in managing costs and income. The higher the NPM, the more efficient the bank is in managing costs and earning income, which in turn can improve the bank's financial performance and PBV. Therefore, NPM can have a positive impact on PBV.

(41) Non Performing Loans/NPL. NPL is a ratio that measures the quality of bank assets. The higher the NPL, the more bank assets are considered at risk and cannot be recovered, which can lead to a decline in the bank's financial performance and PBV. Therefore, NPLs can have a negative impact on PBV.

(42) PSAK 50/55. PSAK 50/55 is a financial accounting standard that regulates the recognition, measurement and presentation of financial instruments. Consistent and appropriate application of accounting standards can increase investor confidence and encourage better bank financial performance, which in turn can have a positive impact on PBV.

(43) Price Earning Ratio/PER. Price Earning Ratio (PER) is a ratio used to assess how expensive or cheap a share price is compared to earnings per share. In the banking context, PER can influence PBV because the higher the PER, the higher the share price valuation. This can provide a positive signal regarding company performance and potential profits in the future, which in turn can increase PBV.

(44) Investment opportunities. Investment opportunities available in the banking industry can influence PBV. The greater the investment opportunities available, the more likely investors are to buy banking shares and in turn increase demand for shares and PBV. If investment opportunities decline, investors are likely to sell their shares, which can reduce demand for shares and PBV.

(45) Asset growth. Asset growth can affect PBV because the greater the assets owned by the company, the greater the company's market value. In this case, positive asset growth can increase PBV because it increases investors' perceptions of the company's value in the future.

(46) Dividend payout ratio. Dividend payout ratio refers to the share of profits paid as dividends to shareholders. In banking, this ratio is often an indicator of financial stability and a company's ability to pay promised dividends. An increase in the dividend payout ratio can indicate that the company has good financial performance and can maintain profits in the future, thereby increasing PBV and share prices.

(47) Return on capital ratio. The ROE ratio is a measure of management efficiency in generating profits from capital invested by shareholders. An increase in ROE can show management's ability to increase profits and strengthen the company's position in the market, thereby increasing PBV and share prices.

(48) Return On Assets/ROA. The ROA ratio measures how effective a company is in generating profits from the assets it owns. In banking, ROA is often an indicator of management's effectiveness in using assets to generate profits. Increasing ROA can increase investor confidence and show strong financial performance, thereby increasing PBV and share prices.

(49) Return On Equity/ROE. ROE is a financial ratio that measures the rate of return on shareholder equity. A high ROE shows that the company is able to generate higher profits from the capital invested by shareholders. This tends to increase PBV because investors will tend to pay more for shares of companies that have a high ROE.

(50) Stock returns. Stock return is the rate of return received by investors in the form of dividends or increases in share prices. High stock returns tend to increase PBV because investors will tend to buy shares of companies that provide high returns.

(51) Return On Investment/ROI. ROI measures the efficiency of investments made by a company. A high ROI indicates that the company is able to generate higher profits from invested capital. A high ROI tends to increase PBV because investors will tend to pay more for shares of companies that have a high ROI.

(52) Sales Growth. Sales growth, or sales growth, can influence PBV in banking. If sales growth generated by banking increases, it is hoped that profits will also increase. As profits increase, the company value will be higher. Therefore, PBV is also likely to be higher.

(53) Interest rates. Interest rates are an important factor in the banking industry. An increase in interest rates can have an impact on increasing loan interest and vice versa. If interest rates rise, then deposit interest and term savings interest also rise. This can increase interest income and overall banking financial performance. An increase in banking financial performance will encourage an increase in share prices and company value, which can affect PBV.

(54) Ownership structure. Bank ownership structure can also influence PBV. If the majority of share ownership is in the hands of institutions or large shareholders, this can give confidence to the market and increase confidence in the company. In addition, large shareholders who have great influence in the company tend to pay more attention to the company's financial performance and growth. This can motivate company management to improve financial performance and company growth, so that it can influence PBV.

(55) Capital structure. An optimal capital structure can increase company value and have a positive impact on PBV. The higher the debt ratio compared to equity, the higher the risk of default and the lower the company's PBV.

(56) Total Asset Turnover/TATO. The TATO ratio describes how effectively a company uses its assets to generate sales. The higher the TATO ratio, the better the company's performance in maximizing the use of its assets to generate income. Good performance can have a positive impact on PBV.

(57) Tax planning. Tax aggressiveness and tax avoidance can affect a company's PBV. Companies that use aggressive tax avoidance strategies may face reputational and legal risks, which can affect PBV. However, good and conservative tax management can help companies avoid these risks and increase PBV.

(58) Tangible assets. Tangible assets or physical assets owned by a company can influence banking PBV. This is because physical assets can be

collateral or underlying value for the bank. The greater the value of physical assets owned by a bank, the higher the banking PBV tends to be.

(59) Total cash flow. The total cash flow generated by a bank can also influence banking PBV. The greater the cash flow generated, the greater the banking PBV value. This is because large cash flows can indicate good bank performance and large profit potential.

(60) Company size. Company size can influence banking PBV. The larger the company size, the higher the banking PBV tends to be. This is because a large company size can indicate large profit potential and a good reputation.

(61) Working Capital Ratio/WCR. WCR or working capital ratio can affect banking PBV. The higher the working capital ratio, the higher the banking PBV tends to be. This is because a high working capital ratio can show the bank's ability to manage its capital well and efficiently.

Conclusions and Recommendations

Based on the results of the discussion above, it can be concluded as follows: first, based on mapping the distribution of journal publications regarding the Price to Book Value (PBV) ratio in Sharia and Conventional Banking during the period 2003 to 2022 which comes from the accredited national journal Sinta, there are 385 published journal articles. Second, based on the VOSviewer bibliometric study mapping, the network visualization results regarding the PBV ratio in Sharia and Conventional Banking are divided into 4 clusters and 113 topic items. Cluster 1 consists of 42 topics, cluster 2 consists of 36 topics, cluster 3 consists of 33 topics, and cluster 4 consists of 2 topics. Third, based on mapping studies literature review, there are 27 topics related to the influence of the PBV ratio on Sharia and Conventional Banking, namely: stock beta, Beneish M-Score, Debt to Total Asset Ratio, Debt to Equity Ratio/DER, Dividend Payout Ratio/DPR, Earnings Response Coefficient/ERC, Earning Per Share/EPS, Earning Management, stock prices, dividend policy, investment decisions, stock split decision, market performance, company value, dividend distribution, stock valuation, company equity valuation, voluntary disclosure of intangible assets, Price Earning Ratio/PER, Stock portfolio return, Return of Share/ROS, Return On Assets/ROA, Return On Equity/ROE, return of sharia stock issuers, Sales Growth, stock trading volume, and activity volume.

And there are 61 topics related to the determinants of the PBV ratio in Sharia and Conventional Banking, namely: Auditor Switching, Tax Aggressiveness, Assets Ratio, Actuarial Profile, Actuarial Backup, Basic Earning Power/BEP, stock beta, financial burden, Operational Costs to Operating Expenses/BOPO, Capital Adequacy Ratio/CAR, Capital Turnover, Capital Expenditure, Corporate Social Responsibility/CSR, Current Ratio, Deviation of Actual Growth Rate from Sustainable Growth Rate, Degree of Fundamental Leverage, Debt to Asset Ratio/DAR, Dividend Payout Ratio/DPR, Debt to Equity Ratio/DER, Earnings Growth Rate, Earning Per Share/EPS, Earning Management, Economic Value Added/EVA, Financial Leverage, Good Corporate Governance/GCG, Growth, Gross Domestic Product/GDP, inflation, International Financial Reporting Standards/IFRS, Intellectual Capital, financial performance, managerial ownership, dividend policy, investment decisions, net profit, liquidity, Loan to Deposit Ratio/LDR, Long term Debt to Equity Ratio, Net Interest Margin/NIM, Net Profit Margin/NPM, Non Performing Loan/NPL, PSAK 50/55, Price Earning Ratio/PER, investment opportunities, asset growth, dividend payment ratio, return on capital ratio, Return On

Assets/ROA, Return On Equity/ROE, stock return, Return On Investment/ROI, sales growth, interest rates, ownership structure, capital structure, Total Asset Turnover/TATO, tax planning, tangible assets, total cash flow, company size, and Working Capital Ratio/WCR.

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